

Uniting expertise

The integral partnership of educational designers and academics in navigating AI in education

Minh Huynh, Fran Van Den Berg, Osu Lilje, Liana Pozza, and Floris Van Ogtrop

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As an educational designer in the central Educational Innovation team, I [Minh] have collaborated with academic colleagues from the School of Life and Environmental Sciences. Our work has often crossed organisational boundaries and roles, but supporting AI in education presented a unique challenge. This new area required us to navigate changing AI and assessment policies at a central level while providing practical support to teachers and students.

This presentation explored the challenges and opportunities we encountered in integrating AI into education from a third space perspective. We discussed how we worked together within and across teams, between central and faculty units, and with academics, leaders, and others to foster a collaborative environment. Our goal was to share insights on enabling strong partnerships.

To facilitate a meaningful exchange of ideas, we shared a [video](#) highlighting our experiences and a discussion board for attendees to share their stories and ideas. This interactive space allowed participants to revisit and reflect on the discussions. We aimed to gather diverse perspectives on the use of AI in education and shared how we implemented an AI tool called [Cogniti](#) at the University of Sydney. Cogniti supports learning through various applications, including assessment feedback, role play, case studies, and as a Socratic tutor. Our innovations include a Cogniti AI assistant that [expands on marker feedback](#) and a student-facing AI assistant providing [feedback on scientific report](#) drafts

About the authors

Minh Huynh

The University of Sydney

Fran Van Den Berg

The University of Sydney

Osu Lilje

The University of Sydney

Liana Pozza

The University of Sydney

Floris Van Ogtrop

The University of Sydney

Associate professor